

EUROqCHARM

EUROpean Quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution

Deliverable 5.1

Launch and management of dedicated website
and social media

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Nature of the deliverable		
R	Report	
DEC	Websites, patents, filing, etc.	x
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Dissemination level		
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CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Blueprints for standards, recommendations for policy and legislation and support for the establishment of acceptable reference levels and environmental targets will be given. This will include a roadmap for harmonised data collection and management, where policy analysis and coherence will be integral parts. To maximise impact, EUROqCHARM will also establish and consolidate an operational network for plastic monitoring, stimulating Transnational Joint Actions built on existing and future European and international initiatives.

The multi-stakeholder composition of EUROqCHARM puts the group in a unique position to achieve these ambitious goals.

More information on the project can be found at: www.EUROqCHARM.eu

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
CSDP	Communication Strategy and Dissemination Plan
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

This document describes the work carried out by the EUROqCHARM partners ILVO, NIVA and SALT in order to be compliant with WP5, Task 5.1 to develop and launch a brand identity, a dedicated multilingual website and social media to inform stakeholders on the progress of the project. The main objective of Deliverable 5.1 is to report on activities undertaken to effectively share information and make available research results, guidelines and products which will be developed throughout the lifetime of the project. This is of great importance for keeping stakeholders up to date on events and progress.

The EUROqCHARM website will provide general and detailed technical information on the project progress, as well as regular updates about events and open dialogue forums between project partners and stakeholder representatives. EUROqCHARM has a multi-stakeholder approach at its core, therefore the target audiences cover a wide range of stakeholders including representatives from research, academia, NGOs, industries, standardisation and policy making bodies (including intergovernmental bodies), expert working groups and networks, end users and civil society.

The EUROqCHARM website is public and was launched on the 25th February 2021. The website will be actively maintained and updated throughout the duration of the project's life. A comprehensive overview of the website, its content and the strategy for its maintenance are provided in Section 3.

The two other important components of the EUROqCHARM project are its brand identity (Section 2) and social media strategy (Section 4). EUROqCHARM will also collect statistics related to the research of the project (Section 5).

2. Brand Identity

2.1. Strategy

The development of a brand identity, website and social media within EUROqCHARM are meant to (1) make the project and its aims recognisable to fellow scientists and all other stakeholders, (2) ensure that all target audiences are effectively engaged, (3) ensure that project results are taken up so the effect of the effort put in harmonizing methodologies is long-lasting and allows to overcome the comparability challenge.

The communication and dissemination objectives are:

- i) Ensure awareness of the project, objectives and activities by the project stakeholders
- ii) Allow engagement of stakeholders in activities relying on stakeholder engagement and providing legitimisation for advancing in the project strategy
- iii) Dissemination of project results

The website and social media are regarded as complementary and highly connected tools: social media will draw followers to the website and vice versa. Their connection is clear due to the consistent use of brand identity.

2.2. Logo

The **logo** is the basis of the visual identity and reflects three important characteristics of the project:

- It concerns plastic litter and its degradation products
- it is focussed on research methodology and it is a European initiative.

The logo is a combination of the project acronym and a visual element: the letter Q depicted as a magnifying glass showing plastic degrading into microplastics.

The logo is available in colour, in black and white, and in negative (white logo for coloured backgrounds). The logo will be used across all EUROqCHARM communication products including deliverables, reports and presentations by partners at conferences and other physical and online events. The logo is visible in the signature of the email account associated with the project.

When the logo is used in combination with the European flag, both should be of equal size.

2.2.1 Technical information – for publishing

EUROqCHARM Logo font is Frutiger Neue Black

EUROqCHARM Logo colours are:

	DARK BLUE:	LIGHTER BLUE:
RGB: <small>(advised for screen viewing - default)</small>	R21 G70 B91	R50 G178 B233
Hex:	#15465B	#32B2E9
CMYK: <small>(advised for printing)</small>	C92 M60 Y42 K36	C76 M28 Y13 K1

Project partners will use CMYK values for anything that will be printed, and RGB for anything that will be viewed digitally/on a screen. This implies that there can be two slightly different versions of the logo. Therefore, use of colours values must be consistent when used across mediums.

2.3. Font types

For the website, the used font is Flanders Art. As this font is not widely available for all partners, all other products should be based on the generally available Calibri font. That way, documents and presentations remain interchangeable and editable by all partners.

2.4. Colour pallet

The colours defining the EUROqCHARM visual identity are **DARK BLUE** (RGB: R21 G70 B91) and **LIGHTER BLUE** (RGB: R50 G178 B233). These can be complemented by black and white.

2.5. Graphical elements

Graphical elements include the logo and the illustration of a wave. This extra visual element complements the logo and can be used to create visual coherence in derived products.

2.6. Imagery

EUROqCHARM has established a Microsoft Teams and SharePoint platform to provide a central repository of pictures and footage related to the project. Partners can share their visuals for use on the website, in presentations, or other products. The pictures can also be shared with the press upon request, if they are deemed suitable. When a copyright has been specified, it should be mentioned on or below the picture at every use.

As an example, a logo banner has been created for use on the website, conference presentations and other outreach activities.

3. Website

The website provides information on the project, it is a platform for providing updates on project activity and dissemination of outputs; in addition, it provides relevant news to the scientific community and wide network of stakeholders and is facilitating dialogue and networking across the project, its Work Packages and partners. The website is a communication tool which is mainly used within EUROqCHARM to reach research institutes and commercial laboratories, environmental agencies, decision-makers, data-owners and managers, the private sector and other interested end-users.

3.1. Registration Data

EUROqCHARM has its own website at www.euroqcharm.eu which was launched on 25th February 2021. A screenshot of registration by ILVO is shown in Figure 1.

Login servicedesk@belnet.be 02/790.33.00

Beste ILVO DNS Master (Instituut voor Landbouw- en Visserijonderzoek),
 We hebben uw bestelling goed ontvangen en we verwerken die zo snel mogelijk. Dit is het detail van uw bestelling :
 Bestelnummer : **3718141130**
 Domeinnaam registratie: Register
 Domein: euroqcharm.eu
 Eerste betalingsbedrag: €12,00
 Herhalend bedrag: €12,00
 Registratie periode: 1 jaar

Totaal te betalen: €14,52
 U krijgt van ons een e-mail zodra de bestelling is uitgevoerd of er een wijziging is in de status van uw bestelling. Gelieve het bestelnummer mee te geven met iedere correspondentie over deze bestelling.
 Met vriendelijke groeten,
 Bien à vous,
 Best regards,

Belnet - WTC III
 Simon Bolivarlaan 30 Boulevard Simon Bolivar
 1000 Brussels
 BELGIUM

Belnet – WTC III Simon Bolivarlaan 30 Boulevard Simon Bolivar 1000 Brussels BELGIUM www.belnet.be	Our Services General Standard services Plus services Domain name registration DNS service	Contact us servicedesk@belnet.be 02/790.33.00
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3.2. Design and Maintenance

The website is technically managed by CabinetC, that developed its structure and graphic design, and will manage structural changes and technical support. A dedicated staff member of ILVO, the host of the website, is updating the website regularly, sharing news, information on events, presentations and relevant studies. The website will be continuously updated based on top-down input by the project management and bottom-up input by experts involved in the project. This information flow is facilitated by the Newsroom and its quality is controlled by the Communication and Coordination Committee (detailed in the CSDP, Annex). The website is set up to be bilingual, with an English version and a French version. The English version is online since 25th February, the French version will be ready by the end of March 2021. Translation will be coordinated by the website manager. The quality control of the English version is provided by NIVA while AFNOR will ensure the quality control of the French version.

The website is fully responsive and can therefore also be viewed and navigated using a mobile device.

3.3. Sections

3.3.1. Homepage

This is the first view of the EUROqCHARM website for the users. It has been designed to give an at-a-glance impression of the project by choosing a concise (and search engine optimized) description, apt imagery, and a clear overview of partners involved. The homepage includes a subscription link to the newsletter as a call-to-action. All subscriptions to the newsletter will be treated in line with EU GDPR (2016/679) concerning the protection of personal data.

3.3.2. About

The “About EUROqCHARM” section has 4 subsections, describing the rationale of the project (why?), the objectives (what?), the methodology and the work packages (how?).

[Home](#) → [Work Packages](#)

Work Packages

To organize all the ambitions that the EUROqCHARM project has set forward, the work is divided into several work packages that each have their own specific goals, methodologies and partners involved, so that each can reach a specific part of the project objectives.

<p>Work Package 1: Screening and analysis of methods</p> <p>The purpose of this WP is to identify state-of-the-art procedures for sample collection, sample preparation and analysis of plastics from environmental samples to define methods and subsequent tasks.</p>	<p>Work Package 2: Validation of methods</p> <p>EUROqCHARM will validate methods for use in the monitoring and assessment of plastics in environmental matrices to harmonise the sample workflow from preparation to analysis and data reporting.</p>	<p>Work Package 3: Harmonisation</p> <p>The purpose of WP3 is to internationally harmonise monitoring methods and data reporting so that they can be used by stakeholders to formulate and implemented policy and legislation.</p>
<p>Work Package 4: Capacity building</p> <p>WP4 has been specifically designed to facilitate the acceleration and adoption of developed standards and guidelines.</p>	<p>Work Package 5: Knowledge transfer and dissemination</p> <p>WPS will ensure targeted communication, dissemination and exploitation of project results by key actors.</p>	<p>WP 6: Project management</p> <p>WP6 activities are designed to ensure an effective management of the project.</p>

3.3.3. Partners

This section contains information about the 15 partners involved in the project. Each of the partner’s logo provides a link to a specific page within the EUROqCHARM website dedicated on providing more information on that partner’s role in the project, with a link to that partner’s own institute homepage in order to enable the user to access additional information on the partner’s expertise and activities. This part of the website will be static, except in the case of partner changes in the project.

3.3.4. News and publications

This section of the project website will present different outcomes of the EUROqCHARM project. News and publication categories can be viewed and downloaded from this page. This includes press releases, scientific publications, reports, presentations, etc. At the time of the website launch, the project press release is available to view.

3.3.5. Events

This subsection will provide information about the events related to EUROqCHARM and the field of plastic pollution research. Each of the events will include its title, date, place and a brief description. A link to the event will be provided and links to any download material will be also included. This page will be updated when events are arranged.

3.3.6. Contact

The last section of the main page of the website provides contact information. Web users can ask for information, send comments and/or suggestions.

3.4. Navigation

The website structure is composed of primary and secondary navigation from the Homepage. A distinction is made between primary and secondary navigation, visible as different colours in the navigation pane. Whereby, the primary navigation “About EUROqCHARM” has 4 subpages: “Why this project?”, “Objectives”, “The EUROqCHARM methodology” and “Work Packages”. The primary navigation “Partners” has subpages for each of the 15 partners. The subpage “Work Packages” is further divided with a page for each Work Package. The secondary navigation level includes three pages: “News and publications”, “Events” and “Contact”.

The complete navigation tree of the website:

Once the French translations have been made, the French navigation tree will be identical.

4. Social media strategy and platforms

Social media as a communication tool is mainly used within EUROqCHARM to reach research institutes and commercial laboratories, environmental agencies, decision-makers, data-owners and managers, and the private sector (See CSDP, Annex). To date, three of the platforms have been activated (Twitter, ResearchGate and LinkedIn). YouTube, Facebook and Instagram are being considered for suitability.

Social Media platform	Account	Targeted activity	Comments
Twitter	@EUROqCHARM	Periodic related to project activity. Minimum of 3 posts a month and 1000 followers by the end of the project	Launched 25 th February 2021
ResearchGate	Project page: EUROqCHARM	At least one monthly update and 500 follows by the end of the project	Project launched by NIVA partners 25 th February 2021
LinkedIn	<i>Per partner</i>	At least one monthly update	Post will be linked to Twitter and ResearchGate updates
YouTube	-	At least 6 videos over the duration of the project covering activities within the work packages, or recorded presentations by project partners	Pending to be launched later in 2021
Facebook / Instagram	-	Periodic related to project activity. Posts will mirror those across media channels	Pending requiring decision whether these channels will be suitable for EUROqCHARM

4.1. Twitter

The EUROqCHARM consortium has a Twitter account [@EUROqCHARM](https://twitter.com/EUROqCHARM). The Twitter account will be used to provide updates on ongoing work, announce events organized or attended by EUROqCHARM partners, disseminate results and publications and to network with relevant projects, initiatives and stakeholders. The account is managed by the Scientific Project Manager, Amy Lusher (NIVA). Content aimed for dissemination through Twitter will be provided by all partners to the Newsroom (see CSDP, Annex) by providing suggested Twitter message, graphical content (picture, illustration, short video) and background information (links or documents). Partners and experts with own Twitter accounts are asked to interact with EUROqCHARM by tagging in order to strengthen the messaging and to broaden the reach. The quality of the posts will be monitored by the Communication and Coordination Committee (see CSDP, Annex).

4.2. ResearchGate

The EUROqCHARM consortium has a ResearchGate project page. The page will be used to provide updates on ongoing work, announce events organized or attended by EUROqCHARM partners, disseminate results and publications. The target audience of ResearchGate are research scientists actively involved in plastic pollution research. The account is managed by the Scientific Project Manager, Amy Lusher (NIVA) and all project partners with active ResearchGate accounts are added as collaborators and link their laboratories. Content aimed for dissemination through ResearchGate will be provided by all partners to the Newsroom (see CSDP, Annex) by providing suggested message, graphical content (picture, illustration, short video) and background information (links or documents). Partners with their own ResearchGate accounts are asked to interact with EUROqCHARM by tagging the project in order to strengthen the messaging and to broaden the reach. The quality of the posts will be monitored by the Communication and Coordination Committee (see CSDP, Annex).

4.3. LinkedIn

The project does not have a dedicated LinkedIn page. Posts shared on Twitter and Research Gate will be modified to allow project partners to share project updates on their personal or institutional LinkedIn accounts. Content aimed for dissemination through LinkedIn will be provided by all partners to the Newsroom (see CSDP, Annex) by providing suggested LinkedIn message, graphical content (picture, illustration, short video) and background information (links or documents). The quality of the posts will be monitored by the Communication and Coordination Committee (see CSDP, Annex).

5. Statistics and impact tracking

The effectiveness of all the dissemination activities including the website will be periodically analysed. The EUROqCHARM webpage will be tracked by means of Google Analytics. ILVO will build in Google Analytics on each website page to track number of visits and more specifically geographic location, origin (direct search, social media, ...), bounce rate, time spent on website and number of unique and repeated visits. These functionalities will be available by 1st May 2021.

The success of the social media platforms (Twitter, LinkedIn, Research Gate) will be monitored using the built-in statistics including numbers of likes, shares, recommendations and followers.

All the statistics collected will be presented in the EUROqCHARM yearly reports on communication, dissemination and networking activities (D5.2, D5.3, D5.4). These will provide the project with a clear picture of the reach of all communication and dissemination activities. In the table below, the measures of the impact of dissemination have been highlighted, with specific reference to the website. In case the objective is not fulfilled a contingency plan is considered.

	Indicator	Objective	Contingency plan
Website	Monthly visitors	200	Promoting the website on social media (LinkedIn, Twitter etc.) and email (e.g., Newsletter to subscribers)
	Duration of visits	2 min	Re-organise website to make it easier to find relevant items. Upload more attractive content
	Downloads	20	Ensure that links for downloads on other platforms are directed to the website.
	References from external web pages	10	Encourage stakeholders, larger organisations and strategic initiatives to promote the site.

6. Conclusion

EUROqCHARM has launched its dedicated website and social media channels following the requirements as defined in Task 5.1. The Communication Strategy and Dissemination Plan has been developed and the working document (as of 25.2.2021) has been provided as an annex to this document.

The website and social media strategy aim to increase the public awareness of the EUROqCHARM project including the wide range of stakeholders covering research, academia, NGOs, industries, standardisation and policy making bodies (including intergovernmental bodies), expert working groups and networks, end users and civil society.

The website provides information of the project as well as public deliverables, results and publications. Website visitors can find contact details for the consortium if they have specific questions, alternatively, they can sign up to the periodic newsletter.

The website structure is composed of primary and secondary navigation from the Homepage. Whereby, the primary navigation “About EUROqCHARM” has 4 subpages: “Why this project?”, “Objectives”, “The EUROqCHARM methodology” and “Work Packages”. The primary navigation “Partners” has subpages for each of the 15 partners. The subpage “Work Packages” is further divided with a page for each Work Package. The secondary navigation level includes three pages: “News and publications”, “Events” and “Contact”. The whole content of the webpage is public and available in English (launched February 2021) and French (to be launched March 2021).

7. Annex

– EUROqCHARM Communication Strategy and Dissemination Plan (CSDP) - Working file as of 25/02/2021.

EUROqCHARM

EUROpean Quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution

Communication Strategy and Dissemination Plan

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Abstract

This document describes how the European project EUROqCHARM - EUROpean Quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution - will approach communication in the 2020 – 2023 project period. More specifically, the document lays out the background and methodology for developing the communication strategy and identifies the aims and objectives, target groups, tools and main activities for project communication. It also maps the timeline of project communications as well as the responsibilities.

The aim of the document is to provide a common understanding and approach to communication between the partners and external stakeholders. The strategy clarifies what the partners can expect from one another as well as how they can cooperate to achieve joint aims and bigger impact.

If any item in this document is ambiguous, or further assistance or advice is required then please contact the EUROqCHARM Coordination and Communication Committee.

1. Objectives

1.1. Project objective

EUROqCHARM is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded under the EC Horizon 2020 Programme.

The overall objective of EUROqCHARM is to develop optimised, validated and harmonised methods for monitoring and of plastics in the environment, as well as blueprints for standards and recommendations for policy and legislation.

Figure 1. The overall structure of EUROqCHARM according to WPs

EUROqCHARM will **co-develop** these methods and recommendations using a **multi-stakeholder approach**, whereby the project is structured to **bring together relevant stakeholders to enable cooperation and participation in the dialogue, decision making and implementation** of solutions. This step is critical, as the necessary developments require the **engagement and collaboration of researchers and various stakeholders** with a thorough understanding of the complexity arising from the wide array of polymer types and particle sizes dispersed in different environmental matrices. To this end, the **EUROqCHARM partners, advisory board members and associated stakeholders include all relevant research areas** (natural sciences devoted to marine, surface, groundwater, drinking and waste water, soil, air; analytical chemistry etc.), **industry** (instrument manufacturers, plastic producers

and commercial laboratories), **regulators and policy makers** - United Nations (UN), EU and national level - , **standardisation bodies** - European Committee for Standardisation (CEN) and International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO), **professional associations and societies** - e.g., Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC), **and national and international Non-Governmental Organisations** (NGOs). This sets EUROqCHARM in a unique position to coordinate the validation of the available methods and production of harmonised protocols for assessing plastic contamination that are also accessible to less-developed countries.

The project activities are distributed across 7 Work Packages (WPs), each one with a defined scope and objective (Figure 1). These are detailed in the Description of Action (DoA).

1.2. Communication and dissemination objectives

The action's approach also highlights the importance of communication and dissemination activities in order to engage from the very beginning the large number of stakeholders. This successful engagement will in large measure determine the success of the project and largely condition the uptake of methodologies and recommendations.

Therefore, communication and dissemination products and activities within EUROqCHARM aim to (i) ensure that all target audiences are effectively engaged and (ii) uptake of the project results so the effect of the effort put in harmonizing methodologies is long lasting and allows to overcome the comparability challenge. The promotion of the use of harmonized methods, including monitoring strategies, sample collection, specimen preparation, analytical detection and data reporting, through knowledge transfer and capacity building will. Specifically, Work Package 5 «**Knowledge transfer and dissemination**» will ensure targeted communication, dissemination and exploitation of project results by key actors.

The communication and dissemination objectives are:

- i) Ensure awareness of the project, objectives and activities by the project stakeholders
- ii) Allow engagement of stakeholders in activities relying on stakeholder engagement and providing legitimation for advancing in the project strategy
- iii) Disseminate project results

2. Target audiences and their information needs

EUROqCHARM specifically targets research and academia, commercial and public laboratories, analytical instrument manufacturers, standard organizations, monitoring bodies and networks, environmental data managers, policy makers and civil society organizations directly or indirectly engaged in assessment and monitoring of plastic pollution.

A large number of stakeholders pertaining to the groups named above have already been contacted and engaged by the Consortium during the project proposal development phase and are involved in the project through:

- The Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)
- Associated laboratories interested to participate in the ILC
- The Stakeholders and Standardisation Advisory Board (SSAB). The SSAB is divided in two groups: the Industrial Stakeholder Board and the Standardisation Stakeholder Board

In addition to the specific stakeholders involved through the bodies and groups named above a stakeholder mapping per work package will be conducted in order to complete the database of relevant EUROqCHARM stakeholders. Of specific interest for this is task 5.5 devoted to “Coordinating collaboration with other ongoing activities within the EU” and deliverable 4.2 “Handbook of relevant European plastic monitoring entities, projects and initiatives”.

EUROqCHARM is a highly specialized and technical coordination action and so is the bulk of the project audience. Still because the action aimed at the whole of spectrum of actors involved in assessment and monitoring of plastic pollution it is important to devote efforts to the understanding of the whole action and the important driver behind it – the need for harmonization in order allow time and space comparison and status and effectiveness of measures implemented to tackle plastic pollution. This level of overarching information will suit the whole set of stakeholders.

In addition, specialized information linked to the different work packages will be necessary in order to engage adequately the different kinds of stakeholders named above and ensure the legitimation and uptake of the results from each of the work packages and the project as a whole. For this the project consortium will take actions to regularly engage specific stakeholder groups. These actions include:

- knowledge transfer of best practices concerning various issues related to plastic pollution monitoring
- information exchange between key actors from scientific institutions, industries, standardisation bodies and policy makers
- dissemination of recommendations for overcoming identified gaps and weaknesses which prevent effective monitoring

3. Communication Tools

3.1. Visual identity

The **logo** is the basis of the visual identity and reflects three important characteristics of the project: It concerns plastic litter and its degradation products, it is focussed on research methodology and it is a European initiative. The logo is a combination of the project acronym and a visual element: the letter Q depicted as a magnifying glass showing plastic degrading into microplastics.

The logo is available in colour, in black and white, and in negative (white logo for coloured backgrounds). The logo will be used across all EUROqCHARM communication products including deliverables, reports and presentations by partners at conferences and other physical and online events. We encourage all partners to use the logo in any correspondence (e.g. email signatures) while working on the project. The high-resolution versions of the logo can be found on EUROqCHARM Teams in the Logo folder

! When using the logo in combination with the European flag, both should be of equal size.

Technical information – for publishing:

- Logo colours are
 - DARK BLUE:**
 RGB: R21 G70 B91 (advised for screen viewing - default)
 Hex: #15465B
 CMYK: C92 M60 Y42 K36 (advised for printing)
 - LIGHTER BLUE:**
 RGB: R50 G178 B233 (advised for screen viewing - default)
 Hex: #32B2E9
 CMYK: C76 M28 Y13 K1 (advised for printing)
- Logo font is Frutiger Neue Black

Important note: keep into account that the blue colours might look slightly different depending on whether you work with RGB or CMYK values. It is advised to use CMYK values for anything that will be printed, and RGB for anything that will be viewed digitally/on a screen. This implies that there can be two slightly different versions of the logo, so please be consistent in which colour values you use for which medium.

Font types: For the website and project posters/flyers, the used font is Flanders Art. As this font is not widely available for all partners, all other products should be based on the generally available Calibri font. That way, documents and presentations remain interchangeable and editable by all partners.

Colour palette: The colours defining the EUROqCHARM visual identity are **DARK BLUE** (RGB: R21 G70 B91) and **LIGHTER BLUE** (RGB: R50 G178 B233). These can be complemented by black and white.

Graphical elements: graphical elements include the logo and the illustration of a wave. This extra visual element complements the logo and can be used to create visual coherence in derived products.

Imagery: the TEAMS platform of the project provides a central repository of pictures and footage related to the project. Partners can share their visuals for use on the website, in presentations, or other products. The pictures can also be shared with the press upon request, if they are deemed suitable. When a copyright has been specified, it should be mentioned on or below the picture at every use. Pictures showing confidential information should not be shared on the platform.

As an example, a logo banner has been created for use on the website, conference presentations and other outreach activities.

3.2. Project website

EUROqCHARM has its own website at www.euroqcharm.eu. The website provides basic information on the project, it is a platform for providing updates on project activity and disseminating outputs in addition to providing relevant news and facilitating contacts for the project, its work packages and each of its partners. The website will be continuously updated based on top-down input by the project management and bottom-up input by experts involved in the project. The website is set up to be bilingual, with an English version and a French version. Translation will be coordinated by the website manager. The quality control of the English version is provided by NIVA while AFNOR will quality control the French version. The project website is hosted and maintained by ILVO.

3.3. Newsletter

The project website, as a passive information tool, will be complemented by a built-in newsletter. The newsletter allows for active, attention targeted and regular distribution of news to newsletter subscribers. Stakeholders can easily subscribe to the newsletter using a website link. Newsletter subscription should be promoted in all project communication activities by distributing the subscription link.

There will be two editions of the newsletter per year which will be distributed to the newsletter subscribers and published on the website.

3.4. Social media

The EUROqCHARM consortium has a Twitter account @EUROqCHARM. The twitter account will be used to provide updates on ongoing work, announce events organized or attended by EUROqCHARM partners, disseminate results and publications and to network with relevant projects, initiatives and stakeholders. The account is managed by Amy Lusher (NIVA). Content aimed for dissemination through Twitter will be provided by all partners to the Newsroom (see section [below](#)) by providing suggested Twitter message, graphical content (picture, illustration, short video) and background information (links or documents). Partners and experts with own Twitter accounts are asked to interact with EUROqCHARM by tagging in order to strengthen the messaging and to broaden the reach.

The success of the account will be monitored using the built-in Twitter statistics (number of posts, number of followers). The quality of the posts will be monitored by the Communication and Coordination Committee (see [below](#))

3.5. Templates and project flyer

In order to strengthen the visibility of the project and the association of the project results with the project itself a series of templates will be made available to be used for all project outputs.

All **presentations** about EUROqCHARM or its results should use the EUROqCHARM presentation template. This can be found under Project templates on Microsoft Teams. The template provides the EUROqCHARM visuals and suggestions for text formatting. Users are free to add logo and name of the institute of their affiliation. That logo should not be larger than the EUROqCHARM logo.

A template **word document** is provided with a fixed header and footer, and a document version tracker. This template is to be used as the basic template for internal and external reports, meeting agenda and minutes etc.

As most meetings are online due to COVID restrictions, a Teams **background** is provided in EUROqCHARM style.

A visually attractive **flyer** reflecting the essence of the project is made available to all partners in digital and printable format (up to A0 for use as a poster).

3.6. Events as communication tools

In order to promote dissemination and stakeholder involvement, the EUROqCHARM consortium will organise 3 workshops and a final event involving participation from outside the consortium (Tasks 5.2, 5.3, 5.4 and 5.6 – see Gant chart in section [below](#) and task description in Annex).

The events will be widely announced and promoted using the available tools (website, newsletter, Twitter...). During and after the events, consortium members are encouraged to provide testimonials on progress and results, pictures and footage to the Newsroom. This input can then be translated in news items on the same channels used for promotion of the events.

The final event should be widely covered. This should be pursued through active invitation of the press and timely preparation of a press release showcasing the main achievements of the project and highlighting their societal relevance.

4. Procedures

4.1. Requirements for Acknowledgement

There are two options for acknowledging the European Union's funding:

- "This project has received funding from the European Unions' Horizon 2020 Coordination and support action programme under Grant agreement ID 101003805 (EUROqCHARM). This output reflects only the authors view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein."
- "This [infrastructure, equipment, type of results] is part of a project that has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 Coordination and support action programme under Grant agreement 101003805 (EUROqCHARM)."

All EUROqCHARM templates include the acknowledgement/disclaimer.

N.B!! In any public products, the use of the EU emblem including grant number is required in order to acknowledge the European Commission as the funder of the project.

Several versions of the EU emblem can be used, depending on what you need it for, including blue text, black and white text, long version and short version.

This project has received funding from the European Unions' Horizon 2020 Coordination and support action programme under Grant agreement ID 101003805 (EUROqCHARM). This output reflects only the authors view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

This [infrastructure, equipment, type of results] is part of a project that has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 Coordination and support action programme under Grant agreement 101003805 (EUROqCHARM).

4.2. Notification of dissemination or exploitation activities.

It is very important that all dissemination and exploitation activities are reported (there is a template for [reporting dissemination or exploitation activities](#) on Teams) as this is crucial for reporting back on the impact of the project.

The reporting template provides guidance on the kind of information to be reported but it is important to always document the impact of the activities in the best possible way. Impact reporting is complex but at the very least the approximate size of the audience reached is very important specially when activities are time intensive and involving active communication like presentations, workshops or seminars. In addition to information, it is important to provide details of the event through links to the event announcement/programme, files of presentation or poster and if possible graphical documentation (pictures or screenshots if the event is digital).

4.3. Publications

Publishing the work and results of EUROqCHARM is essential to meet project objectives and reach the wide audience envisioned and to have high impact. Partners are encouraged to speak about the project

in public venues and publish the results obtained through the project. In preparing speaking materials and publications partners should focus on their own work and results.

- Any proposed publication relating to the project, including contributions of foregrounds to standards, as well as press releases, shall be sent to the coordinator and all other parties within 30 days.
- Any of the particles may object to the publication within 30 days if, for example, the protection of foreground would be adversely affected by the publication or the publication includes confidential information.

All publications must use one of the following acknowledgement/disclaimers.

- “This project has received funding from the European Unions’ Horizon 2020 Coordination and support action programme under Grant agreement 101003805 (EUROqCHARM). This output reflects only the authors view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.”
- “This [infrastructure, equipment, type of results] is part of a project that has received funding from European Union’s Horizon 2020 Coordination and support action programme under Grant agreement 101003805 (EUROqCHARM). “

5. Responsibilities and timeline

5.1. Organs and groups related to communication and dissemination

5.1.1. Steering Committee

The Steering Committee (SC) is the decision-making body within EUROqCHARM for all significant project issues. Besides day-to-day coordination and financial and administrative management, the SC is responsible for the overall successful project dissemination and communication. More concretely and as defined in the Project Handbook the SC is responsible for:

- Proposing a plan for using and dissemination results to GEA
- Preparing press releases and joint publications by Consortium or proposed by the Funding Authority

Meetings shall be held routinely every three months, and at any time upon written request by 25% of the SC members. These meetings will be held virtually.

Figure 2. Management structure of EUROqCHARM

5.1.2. Communication and Coordination Committee

The Communication and Coordination Committee (CCC) will ensure the appropriate coordination with the corresponding boards at the advisory level and with the WPs at the operational level. The CCC actively ensures a proper linkage between the scientific objectives of the project and adequate dissemination activities beyond the project partners. The CCC is responsible for producing the Communication Strategy and Dissemination Plan (this document) and advises on the design of the visual identity and derived products. The CCC is chaired by WPL 5, Joan Fabres and include the PM, WP4 leader, the newsroom chair and social media responsible. This core team will act as a platform to foster and facilitate dissemination and communication activities.

The Committee will meet every three months, back-to-back with the SC meetings, and ad hoc during the course of the project to evaluate communication opportunities and needs.

The CCC actively identifies strategic dissemination priorities, opportunities and content. The CCC defines the communication output which is then developed, finalized by and distributed through the newsroom.

5.1.3. Newsroom

The Newsroom is chaired by ILVO and unites communication representatives of all partners. The Newsroom will receive and actively request and harvest input for dissemination and communication outputs from WP leaders and project partners. The newsroom members meet at frequent intervals via teleconference or physical meetings at project events. The aim of these meetings is to evaluate topics proposed by project partners and the CCC (raw communication material such as reviews, evaluations

of approaches of data production in member states, methodological issues, guidelines, new practices) and to rewrite them into clear texts, social media posts and website news items.

Members of the newsroom will take care to distribute news items and their links through own existing institutional social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram). This strategy is a win-win-win: 1) it maximises the number of people exposed to EUROqCHARM via dissemination actions by each of the partner organisations; 2) news officers (project partners) can easily translate and customise the messages for their networks; and 3) all news items link back to the information hub - the project website - which results in increased website traffic and a better search engine ranking.

5.1.4. Scientific Advisory Board

The Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) will be instrumental in ensuring the achievement of all project objectives, the quality of the deliverables, dissemination and appropriate exploitation of the key outputs. SABs are an advisory body who will:

- Provide recommendation on scientific development of the project
- Provide consultation on selected project activities
- Validate at high-level results of the project
- Provide critical input on activities of the project
- Provide input to identify developments and technologies of strategic interest,
- **Amplify the dissemination and awareness of the initiative**
- **Contribute to clustering process among the community of European stakeholders.**

Meetings will be held annually so that the SABs can oversee the project developments, results. Ad-hoc meetings or email exchanges may be arranged if the PM or WP leaders require input from SABs affiliated with specific WPs.

5.1.5. Standardization and Stakeholders Advisory Board

The Standardisation and Stakeholders Advisory Board (SSAB) will be instrumental in ensuring the achievement of all project objectives, the quality of the deliverables, **dissemination and appropriate exploitation of the key outputs**. At the beginning of the project, each appointed member of the SSAB will be asked to sign an agreement (including Non-Disclosure Agreement) that will formally define their tasks and responsibilities. Contact details are held by WPL5 and PM.

5.2. Communication and dissemination plan

5.2.1. Project timescale and plan

EUROqCHARM commenced on the 1st November 2020. The project length is 36 months. The project closure date is 31 October 2023.

A simplified GANTT chart can be found in the figure below and the complete GANTT chart for EUROqCHARM can be found in the DoA (part B) and on the TEAMS site in the Key Documents folder.

WP no	WP Name	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3			
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
1	Screening and analysis of existing methods and protocols for plastic pollution monitoring	D1.1				D1.2							
2	Validation of methods for plastics analysis in environmental samples							D2.1	D2.2				D2.3
3	Harmonization: Integrate recommended procedures with policy, legislation and risk assessment									D3.1		D3.2	D3.3
4	WP4 Capacity building										D4.1	D4.2	D4.3
5	WP5 Knowledge transfer and dissemination	D5.1			D5.2	WS1	WS2			D5.3	WS3		D5.4 FE
6	WP6 Project management and coordination				D6.1				D6.2				D6.3
7	WP7 Ethics requirements	D7.1											

Figure 3. Simplified GANT chart for the EUROqCHARM project. The description of the deliverables associated with each WP can be found in Annex 1. WS (Workshop) and FE (Final Event)

EUROqCHARM contains 7 Work Packages (WPs) as detailed in the table figure above. The first three work packages are content generating work packages building on each other and therefore becoming progressively more active and communications relevant as the project timeline advances. WP4, devoted to capacity building, will make use of the outputs of the previous three work packages and is naturally communication and dissemination intensive. The last three WPs entail activity sustained through the whole project life.

The detailed WP and task plan and the deliverables associated to each of the work packages can be found in the Annex.

5.2.2. Deliverables, milestones and events of communication and dissemination significance

Communication and dissemination activities should be focussed and intensified around the submission and distribution of key deliverables, achievement of milestones and celebration of project organized events. The table below summarizes, in chronological order, the deliverables and events of major significance together with the editions of the newsletter and constitutes the timeline for the dissemination plan.

The most adequate dissemination and communication efforts (social media posts, website articles press releases and follow up with media, etc) devoted to each instance will be discussed between the CCC/Newsroom and the responsible partner ahead of the delivery date in order to plan, develop and publish outputs at the right time through the right channels. The targeted output will depend on the nature of the news and the targeted audience. Laboratory activity can for example be communicated through a picture or video clip on Twitter. A scientific publication containing policy recommendations, on the other hand, can be rewritten into a policy brief and be presented to policy makers during a stakeholder event. Important news items will be turned into press releases, upon the decision of the Communication and Coordination Committee. Contacts with the general media (radio, television, written press) can be covered by the local partner or by the press contacts and project coordinator or manager. All press questions should be reported to the Project Manager.

Deliverable /Task number	Deliverable / Event	WP No.	Lead partner	Type of deliverable / Activity	Dissemination level	Delivery date
D5.1	Launch and management of dedicated website and social media	5	ILVO	Websites etc.	Public	M4
NL 1	Newsletter 1 (March 2021)	5	ILVO	Newsletter	Public	M5
NL 2	Newsletter 2 (September 2021)	5	ILVO	Newsletter	Public	M11
D1.1	Critical review of methods and protocols for the analysis of nano-, micro- and macro- plastic in different environmental matrices	1	CNR	Report	Confidential	M15
5.2	Organisation of the workshop with stakeholders on the results from WP	5	ILVO	Workshop	By invitation / public	M17
NL 3	Newsletter 3 (March 2022)	5	ILVO	Newsletter	Public	M17
5.3	Organisation of the workshop with international laboratories participating in the quality control study	5	VUA	Workshop	By invitation / public	M19
D2.1	Evaluation on the results of the interlaboratory study	2	VU	Report	Confidential	M21
D2.2	Feasibility study of the harmonised protocol for use in large scale monitoring programs	2	NIVA	Report	Public	M22
NL 4	Newsletter 4 (September 2022)	5	ILVO	Newsletter	Public	M23
D3.1	Recommendations of procedures and methods for monitoring programs	3	AU	Report	Public	M24
5.4	Organisation of the workshop – “Sampling strategies for plastic litter (from macro to micro and nanoplastics) monitoring in the different environmental compartments”	5	SALT	Workshop	By invitation / public	M27
D4.1	Report on the establishment of Operational Network for Plastic monitoring	4	INCDM-NIMRD	Report	Public	M28
NL 5	Newsletter 3 (March 2023)	5	ILVO	Newsletter	Public	M29
D3.2	Optimisation of monitoring strategies to improve the MSFD strategy	3	IFREMER	Report	Public	M30
D4.2	Handbook of relevant European plastic monitoring entities, projects and initiatives	4	INCDM-NIMRD	Report	Public	M32
D3.3	Standard measuring procedures for policy and legislation (baselines and thresholds)	3	NIVA	Report	Public	M34
D3.4	Report on global database synchronisation	3	OGS	Report	Public	M34
D4.3	Report on development of national and regional plastic litter capacity building action plans	4	INCDM-NIMRD	Report	Public	M34
NL 6	Newsletter 4 (September 2023)	5	ILVO	Newsletter	Public	M35
D4.4	Report on the Transnational Joint Actions	4	INCDM-NIMRD	Report	Public	M36
D2.3	Production of at least two CRMs, and identification of two candidate CRMs	2	CHIRON	Other	Public	M36
5.6	Organisation of the EUROqCHARM Final conference	5	NIVA	Conference	Public	M36

5.2.3. Project internal events of communication and dissemination significance

In addition to the events listed above as part of the project communication and dissemination timeline, the project Annual Meetings and General Assembly meetings are also of significance as their occurrence is worth reporting. They constitute opportunities for interaction amongst project partners for the discussion of communication and dissemination activities. The table below provides the timing for these meetings.

	Meeting Type	Date	Location (partner)
KOM	Kick off meeting	12.11.2020	Online (NIVA)
GEA 1	Ordinary General Assembly 1	16.12.2020	Online (NIVA)
AM 1	First year annual meeting	M12	TBC
GEA 2	Ordinary General Assembly 2	M12	TBC
AM 2	Second year annual meeting	M24	TBC
GEA 3	Ordinary General Assembly 3	M24	TBC
AM 3	Third year annual meeting	M36	Brussels (NIVA)

6. Annex

Work Package, Tasks and Deliverable lists

EUROqCHARM contains the following seven Work Packages (WPs) as detailed in the table below:

WP No.	WP Title	Lead partner	Participants	Start-End
WP1	Screening and analysis of existing methods and protocols for plastic pollution monitoring	CNR	NIVA, SALT, CSIC, NILU, ILVO, AWI, AU, Chiron, EAWAG, OGS, AFNOR	Month 1-15
WP2	Validation of methods for plastics analysis in environmental samples	VU	NIVA, VUA, IFREMER, CSIC, NILU, AWI, AU, Chiron, EAWAG, AFNOR	Month 3-36
WP3	Harmonisation: Integrate recommended procedures with policy, legislation and risk assessment	IFREMER	NIVA, CNR, IFRMER, NILU, ILVO, AWI, AU, EAWAG, OGS, AFNOR	Month 6-36
WP4	Capacity building	INCDM-NIMRD	NIVA, CNR, VUA, SALT, CSIC, NILU, AWI, AU, AFNOR	Month 24-36
WP5	Knowledge transfer and dissemination	SALT	NIVA, VUA, IFREMER, CSIC, NILU, AWI, AU, Chiron, EAWAG, AFNOR, ILVO	Month 1-36
WP6	Project management and coordination	NIVA	All	Month 1-36
WP7	Ethics requirements	NIVA	All	Month 1-36

EUROqCHARM Work Packages are divided into Tasks detailed in the table below:

Task No.	Task Name	Delivery date	Lead partner
1.1	Identification of Reproducible Analytical Pipelines to analyse nano-, micro- and macro-plastics in solid samples	M10	AU
1.2	Identification of Reproducible Analytical Pipelines to analyse nano-, micro- and macro-plastics in aqueous samples	M10	AWI
1.3	Identification of Reproducible Analytical Pipelines to analyse nano-, micro- and macro-plastics in biota samples	M10	ILVO
1.4	Identification of Reproducible Analytical Pipelines to analyse nano-, micro- and macro-plastics in air samples	M10	NILU
1.5	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) analysis of the identified methods	M15	CNR
2.1	Possibilities and needs to CRMs r plastic in solid, liquid and gaseous matrices	M6	VUA
2.2	Producing analytical standard candidate CRM, and candidate matrix CRMs	M36	Chiron
2.3	Organising one or more intercalibration studies using the candidate CRM with associated laboratories	M21	VUA
2.4	Statistical validation of the ILC results	M22	VUA
2.5	Feasibility study of the methods for monitoring studies in terms of analytical uncertainty, applicability and costs	M23	NIVA
2.6	Certification of reference materials	M36	VUA
3.1	Recommendations of most appropriate protocols and methods for monitoring programs	M25	AU
3.2	Identification of the most appropriate monitoring strategies	M31	IFREMER
3.3	Recommendation of standard measuring procedures for policy and legislation	M34	EAWAG
3.4	Synchronisation of European procedures on a global level and alignment with existing approaches and databases	M34	OGS
4.1	Operational network for Plastic Monitoring	M36	NIMRD
4.2	Capacity building for policy analysis and policy coherence	M36	NIMRD
4.3	Transnational Joint Actions	M36	NIMRD
5.1	EUROqCHARM brand identity: information and tools sharing through dedicated website and social media channels.	M36	ILVO
5.2	Organisation of the workshop with stakeholders on the results from WP	M17	ILVO
5.3	Organisation of the workshop with international laboratories participating in the quality control study	M19	VUA
5.4	Organisation of the workshop – “Sampling strategies for plastic litter (from macro to micro and nanoplastics) monitoring in the different environmental compartments”	M27	SALT

5.5	Coordinating collaboration with other ongoing activities within the	M36	SALT
5.6	Organisation of the EUROqCHARM Final conference	M36	NIVA
6.1	Project initiation, activity management and project work plan	M1	NIVA
6.2	Appointment of Scientific Project Manager, Steering Committee (SC), Communication and Coordination Committee (CCC)	M2	NIVA
6.3	Appointment of the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)	M4	NIVA
6.4	Appointment of the Standardisation and Stakeholder Advisory Board (SSAB)	M6	NIVA
6.5	Administrative, financial and legal project management	M36	NIVA
6.6	Project management, coordination and communication	M36	NIVA
7.1	Ethics requirements	M36	NIVA

Each Work Package has a series of planned deliverables detailed in the table below in order of delivery:

Deliverable number	Deliverable title	WP No.	Lead partner	Type of deliverable	Dissemination level	Delivery date
D5.1	Launch and management of dedicated website and social media	5	ILVO	Websites etc.	Public	M4
D5.2	First year report on communication, dissemination and networking activities	5	ILVO	Report	Public	M12
D6.1	First year report on project management activities, procedures and tools	6	NIVA	Report	Public	M12
D1.1	Critical review of methods and protocols for the analysis of nano-, micro- and macro- plastic in different environmental matrices	1	CNR	Report	Confidential	M15
D2.1	Evaluation on the results of the interlaboratory study	2	VU	Report	Confidential	M21
D2.2	Feasibility study of the harmonised protocol for use in large scale monitoring programs	2	NIVA	Report	Public	M22
D3.1	Recommendations of procedures and methods for monitoring programs	3	AU	Report	Public	M24
D5.3	Second year report on communication, dissemination and networking activities	5	SALT	Report	Public	M24
D6.2	Second year report on project management activities	6	NIVA	Report	Public	M24
D4.1	Report on the establishment of Operational Network for Plastic monitoring	4	INCDM-NIMRD	Report	Public	M28
D3.2	Optimisation of monitoring strategies to improve the MSFD strategy	3	IFREMER	Report	Public	M30
D4.2	Handbook of relevant European plastic monitoring entities, projects and initiatives	4	INCDM-NIMRD	Report	Public	M32
D3.3	Standard measuring procedures for policy and legislation (baselines and thresholds)	3	NIVA	Report	Public	M34
D3.4	Report on global database synchronisation	3	OGS	Report	Public	M34
D4.3	Report on development of national and regional plastic litter capacity building action plans	4	INCDM-NIMRD	Report	Public	M34
D4.4	Report on the Transnational Joint Actions	4	INCDM-NIMRD	Report	Public	M36
D5.4	Third year report on communication, dissemination and networking activities	5	SALT	Report	Public	M36
D6.3	Third year report on project management activities	6	NIVA	Report	Public	M36
D6.4	Data Management Plan	6	OGS	ORDP	Public	M36
D2.3	Production of at least two CRMs, and identification of two candidate CRMs	2	CHIRON	Other	Public	M36
D7.1	NEC - Requirement No. 1	7	NIVA	Ethics	Confidential	M36